

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS OF PERMANENT PEACE THEORY AS AN EFFECTIVE
METHOD OF INCREASING THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE AT THE
INTERNATIONAL LEVEL****ZhangLei**

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Abstract. Studying the Permanent Peace Theory, as proposed by Immanuel Kant and related concepts in philosophy and international relations, is relevant for several reasons. Kant's "Perpetual Peace" essay is a seminal work in the history of peace philosophy and political thought. It offers insights into the intellectual foundations of peace movements and the historical efforts to prevent conflicts and promote peace.

Keywords: theory of permanent peace, I. Kant, international relations, humanity.

Аннотация. Изучение теории постоянного мира, предложенной Иммануилом Кантом, и связанных с ней концепций в философии и международных отношениях актуально по нескольким причинам. Эссе Канта «Вечный мир» является плодотворным трудом в истории философии мира и политической мысли. Он предлагает понимание интеллектуальных основ движений за мир и исторических усилий по предотвращению конфликтов и укреплению мира.

Ключевые слова: теория постоянного мира, И.Кант, международные отношения, человечество.

Annotatsiya. Immanuil Kant tomonidan taklif qilingan doimiy tinchlik nazariyasini va falsafa va xalqaro munosabatlardagi tegishli tushunchalarni o'rganish bir necha sabablarga ko'ra dolzarbdir. Kantning "Abadiy tinchlik" essesi tinchlik falsafasi va siyosiy fikr tarixidagi muhim asardir. U tinchlik harakatining intellektual asoslari va mojarolarning oldini olish va tinchlikni targ'ib qilish bo'yicha tarixiy sa'y-harakatlar haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: doimiy tinchlik nazariyasi, I. Kant, xalqaro munosabatlar, insoniyat.

Studying the Permanent Peace Theory, as proposed by Immanuel Kant and related concepts in philosophy and international relations, is relevant for several reasons. Kant's "Perpetual Peace" essay is a seminal work in the history of peace philosophy and political thought. It offers insights into the intellectual foundations of peace movements and the historical efforts to prevent conflicts and promote peace.

Shaping International Relations: The ideas presented in the Permanent Peace Theory have had a significant influence on the field of international relations. Concepts like international law, diplomacy, and democratic peace theory are rooted in Kant's ideas. By studying this theory, scholars and policymakers can gain a better understanding of the foundations of international relations and the possibilities for peaceful coexistence.

The principles outlined in the Permanent Peace Theory advocate for peaceful methods of resolving conflicts. Understanding these principles can be valuable for diplomats, policymakers, and international organizations seeking to prevent or manage conflicts through non-violent means.

Kant's idea of cosmopolitanism encourages people to consider themselves as global citizens. This perspective can promote a sense of shared humanity and the idea that we all have a

stake in preventing global conflicts and addressing global challenges, such as climate change, poverty, and public health crises.

In a world with ongoing conflicts and geopolitical tensions, the study of permanent peace theories remains highly relevant. It offers a framework for analyzing current international relations and exploring potential solutions to global challenges.

Human Rights and Justice: Kant's emphasis on the rule of law and the rights of individuals has contributed to the development of modern human rights principles and the pursuit of justice on a global scale. Studying his ideas can help individuals and societies better understand the foundations of human rights and justice.

The study of Permanent Peace Theory can inspire individuals to become advocates for peace, human rights, and international cooperation. It provides a theoretical basis for those interested in working toward a more peaceful and just world. Kant's philosophy, including his ideas about peace and ethics, challenges individuals to think critically about their moral and political choices. It encourages discussions about the ethical responsibilities of individuals and nations in a global context.

"Permanent Peace" is a concept in philosophy that is closely associated with the ideas of Immanuel Kant, a prominent 18th-century German philosopher. Kant's ideas on perpetual or permanent peace are primarily outlined in his essay titled "Perpetual Peace: A Philosophical Sketch," published in 1795. In this essay, Kant argued for several key principles that, if followed, could lead to a lasting state of peace among nations. These principles include:

Kant believed that the best way to promote peace is through republican (representative) forms of government. He argued that democratic and accountable governments are less likely to wage war, as decisions to go to war would be made by the people, who typically suffer the most during conflicts.

Kant proposed that a system of international laws and treaties should be established to govern the relations between nations. This legal framework would help resolve disputes without resorting to war.

Kant suggested that nations should reduce their standing armies, as large military forces can be a temptation to wage war. Instead, he proposed the idea of a "peaceful militia" that could be called up in times of conflict but would otherwise be engaged in peaceful activities.

Kant's idea of cosmopolitanism encourages individuals to consider themselves as global citizens, rather than simply as members of a particular nation. This cosmopolitan mindset could foster a sense of shared humanity and reduce the likelihood of wars based on nationalistic sentiments.

Kant's "Perpetual Peace" essay is often considered a foundational work in the study of international relations and political philosophy. It laid the groundwork for the development of modern theories on international cooperation, diplomacy, and the quest for lasting peace. While his ideas have been influential, the attainment of permanent peace remains a complex and challenging goal, as international relations are shaped by a myriad of political, economic, and cultural factors. After the baptism of the first industrial revolution, the productivity of the whole European society has been greatly enhanced, objectively promoting the vigorous development of capitalism, which makes the European continent between the old and new classes continue to intensify the contradictions between the state between the state, the state and the state of the frequent outbreaks of war in the Enlightenment under the impetus of European philosophers began to European war and strife of the state of the society for rational reflection. Kant's philosophy was

influenced by Hume and Rousseau in this period, and came out of the dilemma of dogmatism, and began to inquire into the origin of man. Based on the environment of the times

Based on the drastic change of the times and the shift of Kant's own conception, Kant believed that the rational endowment of human beings could only be stimulated and utilized in a civil society with universal rule of law, and the establishment of a civil society depended on the formation of the rule of law within the country, and the expansion of the civil society to the world required the construction of a legitimate external international relationship and a league of nations, so Kant wrote *On Perpetual Peace* to systematically elaborate his related ideas, and in this work Kant wrote *On Perpetual Peace* to systematically elaborate his related ideas. In this work, Kant puts forward two norms of international law for the establishment of permanent peace, namely, the "Temporary Provisions for a Permanent International Peace" and the "Definitive Provisions for a Permanent International Peace", the "Temporary Provisions" being the six "aspects" of the "permanent peace", and the "Definitive Provisions for a Permanent International Peace". The "temporary provisions" are six aspects that "allow countries preparing for and in the midst of war to retain the possibility of ending the war and stepping into permanent peace" It clarifies what is permissible and what is prohibited in the international conduct of States: the "Definitive Clause" defines the norms of international law governing international relations in terms of republicanism, international juridical power and international goodwill, and argues for the elimination of the factors affecting the antagonisms of human civilization.

Kant's idea of permanent peace contains both a macroscopic view of the world vision of human development and a microscopic understanding of the dialectical thinking of human contradictions, which is of great significance to the construction of a community of human destiny. The construction of a community of human destiny is based on the crisis of global modernity and the wholeness of production and life faced by mankind at the present stage, and it is a sublimation of Kant's idea of permanent peace from the idea of globalization, historicity, realism and possibilities. Sublimation, in addition, in dealing with the issue of war and peace, Kant is not a wholesale boycott of war but adhere to the dialectical point of view that war and peace are dialectical unity, peace comes out of the war, without war will not cherish the peace, this understanding of the development of human society of the dialectical thinking of the construction of the community of human destiny has an important significance in guiding the community of human destiny. The concept of a community of human destiny critically rejects and historically transcends Kant's view, resolutely opposes unjust wars, and insists on the central position of the United Nations in international affairs. Individual sovereign states should not only respect the rights and interests of sovereign states and follow universal international rules, but also fulfill their international obligations and assume common but differentiated international responsibilities, and respect the independence and characteristics of sovereign states.

In summary, the study of the Permanent Peace Theory is relevant because it offers insights into the history and philosophy of peace, shapes international relations theory and practice, and promotes the idea that peaceful conflict resolution and cooperation among nations are attainable goals. It remains a valuable area of study for those interested in the pursuit of peace and justice on a global scale.

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